

Composite run around primes

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Abstract

We prove that for every positive even integer $2n$, there exist infinitely many sequences of $2n - 1$ consecutive composite integers, with each sequence immediately followed or preceded by a prime. Our approach uses factorial and primorial constructions combined with Dirichlet's theorem on arithmetic progressions, yielding explicit formulas that determine the positions of these sequences. This result offers new insights into the distribution of primes relative to consecutive composite numbers.

1. Introduction

It is well known that for every integer $m > 1$, there exists a sequence of m consecutive integers containing no primes [3]. This result can be established using the following factorial construction:

$$(1.1) \quad (x + i)_{i=0}^{m-1}, \quad \text{where } x = (m + 1)! + 2.$$

We aim to reformulate Equation (1.1) so that the sequence of m composite integers is bounded by odd integers on both sides. We then show that, for an arbitrary sequence length $2n$, such sequences occur infinitely often within the set of positive integers. Notably, their occurrence follows a pattern of arithmetic progressions, which enables us to invoke Dirichlet's theorem for further constructions. This leads us to examine whether one of the sequence bounds can be an odd prime infinitely often, independently of the other bound. We show that Dirichlet's theorem imposes a coprimality constraint on sequences of consecutive composite integers

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that end at a prime; however, that coprimality constraint becomes irrelevant for sequences of consecutive composite integers that start at a prime.

2. Preliminaries

Consider Equation (1.1). Observe that x is even for all m . Moreover, the sequence starts at x and ends at $x + m - 1$. Let c be a composite integer such that $x - 1 < c < x + m$, with m odd. In this case, $x - 1$ and $x + m$ are positive odd integers lying exactly one unit outside the sequence in (1.1). We define these as the sequence bounds, and their difference is

$$(x + m) - (x - 1) = m + 1.$$

Since $m + 1$ is even, we may write $m + 1 = 2n$, so that $m = 2n - 1$. Since $m > 1$, it follows that $2n > 2$. Substituting into (1.1) gives:

$$(2.1) \quad (x + i)_{i=0}^{2n-2}, \quad \text{where } x = (2n)! + 2 \text{ and } 2n > 2,$$

such that $x - 1 < c < x + 2n - 1$. Certainly, $x - 1$ and $x + 2n - 1$ are odd integers, and the distance between them is

$$(x + 2n - 1) - (x - 1) = 2n.$$

Note that the sequence contains $2n - 1$ terms, and all variables are non-negative integers.

3. Generalization

Lemma 3.1. *Every even integer $2n > 0$ can be expressed in infinitely many ways as the difference of two odd integers with no primes between them.*

Proof. The case $2n = 2$ is trivial. For $2n > 2$, we extend Equation (2.1) as follows:

$$(3.1) \quad (x + i)_{i=0}^{2n-2}, \quad \text{where } x = k \cdot (2n)! + 2,$$

with $k \in \mathbb{Z}^+$ and $2n > 2$. We now show that every integer in the sequence from $i = 0$ to $i = 2n - 2$ is composite for every k . In general, the sequence is

$$x, x + 1, x + 2, \dots, x + i, \dots, x + (2n - 2).$$

Note that

$$\begin{aligned} x &= k \cdot [1 \cdot 2 \cdot 3 \cdot 4 \cdot 5 \cdots 2n] + 2, \\ x &= k \cdot 2 \cdot [1 \cdot 3 \cdot 4 \cdot 5 \cdots 2n + 1]. \end{aligned}$$

Since x is a product of multiple integers then it is composite. Extending this procedure to the subsequent term, $x + 1$, gives:

$$\begin{aligned} x + 1 &= k \cdot [1 \cdot 2 \cdot 3 \cdot 4 \cdot 5 \cdots 2n] + 3, \\ x + 1 &= k \cdot 3 \cdot [1 \cdot 2 \cdot 4 \cdot 5 \cdots 2n + 1]. \end{aligned}$$

Thus, $x + 1$ is also composite. More generally, for any arbitrary term $x + i$ within the range $0 \leq i \leq 2n - 2$, we have:

$$\begin{aligned} x + i &= k \cdot [1 \cdot 2 \cdot 3 \cdot 4 \cdot 5 \cdots 2n] + (i + 2), \\ x + i &= k \cdot (i + 2) \cdot [1 \cdot 2 \cdot 3 \cdots (i + 1) \cdot (i + 3) \cdots 2n + 1]. \end{aligned}$$

Hence, $x + i$ is composite as well. Since there are infinitely many positive integers k , it follows that there exist infinitely many sequences of $2n - 1$ consecutive composite integers. Furthermore, the absolute difference between the odd integers $x - 1$ and $x + 2n - 1$ is $2n$. \square

We now optimize Equation (3.1) by replacing the factorial $(2n)!$ with the primorial $(2n)\#$ which eliminates redundant prime factors. Hence, the refinement of Equation (3.1) is given by the following explicit formula:

$$(3.2) \quad (x + i)_{i=0}^{2n-2}, \quad \text{where } x = k \cdot (2n)\# + 2, \quad 2n > 2,$$

with $x - 1 < c < x + 2n - 1$. To simplify notation, we define this interval as $f < c < g$. By substitution, we obtain the following arithmetic progressions:

$$(3.3) \quad f = k \cdot (2n)\# + 1,$$

$$(3.4) \quad g = k \cdot (2n)\# + 2n + 1.$$

4. A Dirichlet perspective

Lemma 4.1. *For every even integer $2n > 0$, there exist infinitely many sequences of $2n - 1$ consecutive composite numbers that appear immediately after a prime.*

Proof. The case $2n = 2$ is trivial. Consider Equations (3.2) and (3.3). Since f is odd for all k , follows that f corresponds to both odd composites

and odd primes. Recall the Dirichlet prime number theorem [1, 2], which states that “for every two coprime positive integers a and d , there exist infinitely many primes of the form $a + nd$, where n is a non-negative integer, forming an arithmetic progression”.

Clearly, for every $2n$, the numbers

$$f = 1 + k \cdot (2n)\#$$

form an arithmetic progression, it contains 1 and $(2n)\#$ coprime, and k is a non-negative integer. By Dirichlet’s theorem, it follows that infinitely many primes are represented by f . Then, by Lemma 3.1, each prime represented by f is immediately followed by a sequence of $2n - 1$ consecutive composite integers. \square

Lemma 4.2. *For every even integer $2n > 2$ with $(2n)\#$ and $2n + 1$ coprime, there exist infinitely many sequences of $2n - 1$ consecutive composite number that appear immediately before a prime.*

Proof. Under the hypothesis, for every arbitrary $2n$, the numbers

$$g = 2n + 1 + k \cdot (2n)\#$$

form an arithmetic progression satisfying Dirichlet’s theorem. Hence, there exist infinitely many primes represented by g . By Lemma 3.1, each such prime is immediately preceded by a sequence of $2n - 1$ consecutive composite integers. \square

Note that f contains 1 and $(2n)\#$ coprime for all $2n$. However, g does not contains $2n + 1$ and $(2n)\#$ coprime for all $2n$. Therefore, g is subject to coprimality constraints. Certainly, if $2n + 1$ is prime, then $2n + 1$ and $(2n)\#$ are coprime because that prime is not in the factorization of $(2n)\#$. In this case, g may be composite or prime infinitely often. Conversely, if $2n + 1$ is composite, then it is not coprime to $(2n)\#$ and g is always composite.

Theorem 4.3. *For every positive even integer $2n$, there exist infinitely many sequences of $2n - 1$ consecutive composite integers occurring immediately after or before a prime.*

Proof. The case $2n = 2$ is trivial. Lemma 4.1 establishes the result for f . If $2n + 1$ and $(2n)\#$ are coprime, then Lemma 4.2 applies. If $2n + 1$ and $(2n)\#$ are not coprime, then g is always composite; however, the next

prime after g is preceded by a sequence of $2n - 1$ consecutive composite integers. \square

5. Numerical evidence

A numerical example is always useful for developing a deeper understanding of mathematical problems. Table 1 presents different values of $2n, k, f$ and g for $2n > 2$. The case $2n = 8$ illustrates the coprimality constraint imposed by Dirichlet's theorem on arithmetic progressions. When $2n = 8$, we have that $(2n)\# = 210$ and $2n + 1 = 9$. Since 210 and 9 are not coprime, $\gcd(210, 9) \neq 1$; then, every g is always composite, as shown in Table 1. However, without loss of generality, the next prime after $g \in \{219, 429, 639, 849, \dots\}$ is preceded by a sequence of $2n = 8$ composites. Another point of view is to take the next prime after $2n + 1 = 9$ such that it is coprime to $(2n)\#$. Since 11 is the next prime after 9, then in the case $2n = 11 - 1 = 10$ there exist infinitely many sequences of 8 consecutive composite integers, each immediately before a prime.

As mentioned, this coprime constraint occurs whenever $2n + 1$ is composite; that is, when $2n \in \{8, 14, 20, 24, 26, 32, 34, 38, 44, 48, 50, \dots\}$. In relation to Table 1, we have verified that every integer inside the intervals (f, g) , i.e., excluding f and g , are composites.

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Table 1: Pairs of odd integers f and g shown as (f, g) . Primes are with a hat.

$2n=$	4	6	8	10	...
$f=$	$6k + 1$	$30k + 1$	$210k + 1$	$210k + 1$...
$g=$	$6k + 5$	$30k + 7$	$210k + 9$	$210k + 11$...
$k = 1$	$(\hat{7}, \hat{11})$	$(\hat{31}, \hat{37})$	$(\hat{211}, 219)$	$(\hat{211}, 221)$...
$k = 2$	$(\hat{13}, \hat{17})$	$(\hat{61}, \hat{67})$	$(\hat{421}, 429)$	$(\hat{421}, \hat{431})$...
$k = 3$	$(\hat{19}, \hat{23})$	$(91, \hat{97})$	$(\hat{631}, 639)$	$(\hat{631}, \hat{641})$...
$k = 4$	$(25, \hat{29})$	$(121, \hat{127})$	$(841, 849)$	$(841, 851)$...
$k = 5$	$(\hat{31}, 35)$	$(\hat{151}, \hat{157})$	$(\hat{1051}, 1059)$	$(\hat{1051}, \hat{1061})$...
$k = 6$	$(\hat{37}, \hat{41})$	$(\hat{181}, 187)$	$(1261, 1269)$	$(1261, 1271)$...
$k = 7$	$(\hat{43}, \hat{47})$	$(\hat{211}, 217)$	$(\hat{1471}, 1479)$	$(\hat{1471}, \hat{1481})$...
$k = 8$	$(49, \hat{53})$	$(\hat{241}, 247)$	$(1681, 1689)$	$(1681, 1691)$...
$k = 9$	$(55, \hat{59})$	$(\hat{271}, \hat{277})$	$(1891, 1899)$	$(1891, \hat{1901})$...
$k = 10$	$(\hat{61}, 65)$	$(301, \hat{307})$	$(\hat{2101}, 2109)$	$(2101, \hat{2111})$...
\vdots	\vdots	\vdots	\vdots	\vdots	\ddots

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